

Practices and Policies in the Sustainable Climate Transition of VOD

Avenues for European Union–Latin America cooperation

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Citation

Rossato Fernandes, Marina and Dâmaso, Mafalda (2026). Practices and Policies in the Sustainable Climate Transition of VOD: Avenues for European Union–Latin America cooperation, Horizon Europe project StreamSCAPES (ID: 101177811).

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1st Edition 2026

StreamSCAPES URL at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/streamscapes/>

Executive Summary

StreamSCAPES brings together a consortium of twelve organisations, composed of academic institutions and key representatives of creative and cultural industries (CCIs), to explore the under-utilised strengths, existing challenges and knowledge, practice and policy gaps in the Video-On-Demand (VOD) services in Europe, which hinder or enable their sustainable climate transition (SCT).

This publication presents insights from the first phase of the project, which focused on mapping existing policies, practices, challenges, and needs related to SCT in the European VOD sector,¹ combined with emerging findings from the second phase of the project. The findings are based on two research strands: policy mapping and industry practices mapping. The policy mapping examined existing legislative and policy frameworks related to SCT and VOD in order to better understand how different countries are addressing the intersection between SCT objectives and the audiovisual sector. The study covered Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, the Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Sweden and North Macedonia. The mapping combined desk research on legislation and support instruments with 16 interviews.

The industry practices mapping focused on understanding how professionals working in and with VOD platforms perceive and operationalise sustainability in their everyday activities. Five online workshops involving 24 participants were organised in 2025 to discuss the social relevance of SCT, sustainability in production and distribution, and existing policy and industry initiatives. In addition, 13 semi-structured interviews were conducted online between November 2025 and March 2026 with professionals working in European VOD platforms, including several independent services. The interviews explored existing SCT practices, challenges, motivations and barriers across the VOD value chain, including production, distribution and consumption.

These findings provide a preliminary overview of how SCT is currently understood and implemented across the European VOD ecosystem, while also identifying key structural challenges and areas requiring further coordination, knowledge exchange and policy development. Moreover, the brief identifies three policy needs identified by European stakeholders (increase knowledge and knowledge exchange; harmonise; address sectoral asymmetries) and three policy avenues to strengthen cooperation between the European Union (EU) and Latin America in this policy field (co-develop future scenarios for the green transition; rethink the global digital infrastructure; address conceptual and operational blind spots in EU audiovisual policy supporting the sustainable climate transition).

¹ See Keinonen Heidi, Katharine Sarikakis, Pedro Tinen, Marina Rossato Fernandes, Antonios Vlassis, Pauline Bissot, Solenn Houard, Sergio Goffredo, Mafalda Dâmaso, Heritiana Ranaivoson, Marlen Komorowski (2025), PlaySCAPES: Set-the-Stage Report on Sustainable Climate Transition and VOD platforms, Horizon Europe project StreamSCAPES (ID: 101177811). Visit: <https://www.streamscapes.eu>

Key findings

Practices are limited and fragmented

Production

The findings reveal important differences in how SCT is understood and implemented across the audiovisual value chain. Practices related to environmental sustainability are considerably more developed in production than in distribution and consumption.

In production, professionals reported increasing familiarity with sustainability frameworks, carbon calculators, certification schemes, and green production protocols. Sustainability requirements are gradually becoming integrated into funding schemes and commissioning processes, particularly among larger broadcasters and public institutions. However, the development of this integration remains largely uneven across European territories. Likewise, the sector still lacks harmonised standards and measurement systems.

Different actors rely on different tools, methodologies, and certifications, creating fragmentation and reducing comparability across projects and territories. Such fragmentation can create additional challenges for international co-productions, where partners may follow different sustainability requirements, as well different measurement and reporting practices.

At the same time, most European VOD platforms are not yet systematically introducing sustainability requirements in commissioning processes or requiring sustainability criteria from content providers.

Digital Distribution

The research findings point to the lack of reliable data, shared methodologies, and operational guidance regarding the environmental impact of streaming distribution.

Although many organisations expressed willingness to engage with sustainability targets, professionals participating in the study repeatedly stressed that they often do not know how to effectively measure, interpret, or reduce the environmental impact associated with distribution infrastructures.

A central concern is the high dependency on third-party infrastructure. Most European VOD services, particularly Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), rely heavily on external providers for cloud services, data storage, content processing, and content delivery networks, many of which are operated by large international companies.

As a result, platforms frequently lack access to detailed environmental data concerning the infrastructures on which their services depend. Additionally, as frequently stated by participants, environmental impact is not a priority criteria when selecting providers.

Consumption

Most interviewed VOD services already allow users to manually reduce video resolution or adjust playback settings. However, only a very small number actively explain the environmental implications of these choices to audiences.

Professionals agreed that more communication and audience engagement are needed in this area. Nevertheless, they also stressed the complexity of communicating sustainability issues without negatively affecting user experience or creating resistance among audiences.

Participants described a tension between encouraging more sustainable consumption practices and maintaining platform usability, accessibility, and competitiveness. As a result, many companies remain hesitant to introduce visible sustainability messaging or stronger interface interventions.

The mapping of policies suggest there is growing momentum

Advances are enabled by bottom-up and top-down initiatives

In the case of Member State policies, the landscape is characterised by a general lack of national policies targeting VOD services and by broader disparities in knowledge, initiatives, and the linkages between sustainability and audiovisual media policies. However, there are some positive examples. Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden co-developed the Nordic Ecological Standard, which provides a sustainable production framework for the entire audiovisual industry and may become a funding requirement by national bodies. Denmark's reporting requirements (particularly, the inclusion of carbon calculators in production plans) boost greening practices among broadcasters and streaming platforms. Similarly, the support provided by the French Agency for Ecological Transition (ADEME) for collecting energy consumption data has been useful in advancing the conversation, whereas the French Regulatory Authority for audiovisual and digital communication (Arcom) promotes sustainable distribution practices in the industry. That said, the post-production and consumption phases remain the weakest links in these initiatives.

Similarly, several EU policies support the green transition in the audiovisual field. In particular, one must mention the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the sustainability requirements introduced in MEDIA funding schemes that can benefit VOD services. The CSRD impacts large VOD platforms (i.e., with 250 or more employees, €50m or more in net turnover, or €25m or more in total assets), setting up reporting requirements regarding their environmental,

social, and governance (ESG) impact. CSRD nudges VOD platforms to strengthen internal practices and processes for collecting data and tracking performance, including in the case of small- and medium-sized companies that work with such large players. Moreover, Creative Europe's MEDIA programme, which funds the European audiovisual sector, increasingly motivates audiovisual stakeholders to develop environmental strategies and internal practices that enhance the sustainability of their operations, as exemplified by the MEDIA Carbon Calculator.

Harmonisation versus diversity

European stakeholders agree on the need for policies that standardise carbon measurement, improve comparability, and increase transparency across the production, post-production, distribution and consumption levels to scale up existing initiatives and leverage the global power of the Single Market to raise standards. Moreover, they recognise the structural imbalances that characterise the global VOD ecosystem. This underscores the need for European-wide standards to scale up and accelerate current initiatives to make the audiovisual sector sustainable.

However, interviewees from European Member States where the conversation is already advanced are concerned that European-wide agreements might result in restricting low common denominators that prioritise measurement over impact, while small or independent players are concerned over the potential administrative burden required to comply with complex obligations. To provide space for innovation and diversity of approaches, some suggest sector-based coordination through structured dialogues rather than rigid European rules. Others call on the European Union to set a Directive (which would set binding objectives but leave Member States free to choose how to achieve them) rather than a Regulation. In any case, there's demand for effective policies that continue to raise sustainability standards in the European audiovisual sector.

Multiple understandings of environmental sustainability

Emerging findings from the second phase of the project suggest that European policymakers and industry professionals do not share a common definition of sustainability. This can range from lowering the sector's carbon footprint (a goal that can be implemented with multiple, highly divergent methods) to a holistic understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which originally combine environmental, economic, and social impact, expanded by such stakeholders to the cultural sector. In practice, this results in profound contradictions in the operationalisation of green audiovisual policies across Europe. For example, to lower their carbon footprint, independent VOD platforms are often constrained to choose affordable Content Delivery Network providers whose governance models are not aligned with the SDGs.

Policy Recommendations

Increase knowledge and knowledge exchange

Advancing SCT in the VOD sector requires the development of clearer definitions, shared vocabularies, harmonised metrics and more accessible guidance on how environmental impact can be measured, interpreted and reduced across different stages of the audiovisual value chain. There is also a need to strengthen knowledge exchange across the sector by creating spaces for dialogue and collaboration between industry players and policymakers.

Harmonise

The findings demonstrate that current SCT practices and policy approaches remain highly fragmented. Different actors rely on different standards, metrics and reporting systems, limiting comparability and creating obstacles for international cooperation, including international co-productions. The absence of harmonised frameworks also increases the risk of greenwashing, particularly when sustainability claims are based on non-comparable or insufficiently transparent methodologies.

Address sectoral asymmetries

SCT policies and regulatory frameworks must account for the structural realities of the European VOD ecosystem, which is largely composed of SMEs and independent services operating with uneven levels of financial and technical capacity. Future policy approaches should therefore avoid disproportionate compliance burdens on smaller actors and instead support proportionate and adaptable mechanisms that facilitate participation across the sector.

Co-develop future scenarios for the green transition

To strengthen (and, in most cases, initiate) SCT cooperation between European and Latin American film stakeholders, it is necessary to ensure that both groups are aware of existing policies and practices on both sides of the Atlantic. European stakeholders have a limited understanding of the regulatory frameworks that are in place across different European countries. Similarly, they are unaware of ongoing developments in Latin America. Forthcoming StreamSCAPES reports will provide detailed summaries of the European landscape in this context. However, there is a need for sustained opportunities for stakeholders on both sides to come together and learn from one another.

Similarly, despite sharing common challenges, European stakeholders regularly call for (but are unable to articulate) common European policies and initiatives to address their shared needs. Given that some of these challenges are international, if not global (e.g., market power

imbalances, limited technical capacity, and current data infrastructure), policymakers could foster fora for European and Latin American film professionals to co-create future scenarios for the green transition.

Rethink the global digital infrastructure

Interviews with policymakers suggest that their efforts to make audiovisual production and distribution more sustainable and embedded in local ecosystems are hindered by market imbalances and the global digital infrastructure. Moreover, industry stakeholders face the dilemma of wanting to scale their VOD platforms sustainably while competing with powerful actors that do not face such constraints. For this reason, achieving the SCT of the European audiovisual sector requires changing the global digital infrastructure – and this, in turn, demands fostering international collaboration among like-minded stakeholders. Policymakers could create opportunities for European and Latin American stakeholders active or interested in the green audiovisual policy space to innovate and co-develop alternative digital governance frameworks that place sustainability at their core – without having to wait for broader agreements (e.g. supported by the World Trade Organisation or the European Commission).

Address conceptual and operational blind spots in EU audiovisual policy supporting the sustainable climate transition

Interviews with European policymakers reveal significant divergence in the concepts of sustainability and the theories of change that underlie their work. Additionally, they rarely engage with Global South theories and scholarship – such as seven-generation stewardship, buen vivir (living well), and ubuntu (humanity to others). This echoes the findings of previous research, which revealed scope to expand the theoretical underpinnings of European cultural diversity policy discourse and, in doing so, the European approach to the inclusion of culture in the implementation and revision of the Sustainable Development Goals. EU-Latin America cooperation could support European stakeholders in identifying and addressing conceptual and operational blind spots in EU audiovisual policy and in European global policies towards cultural sustainability.

Discover more information and stay updated with the project's research findings on the [StreamSCAPES website](#)

Participate in our [survey](#) to help us better understand the role that Video-on-Demand platforms can play in advancing the Sustainable Climate Transition. Once completed, you will be given a chance to be entered into a draw for one of two free Marché du Film 2027 accreditations.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.